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WORKSHOP ON REMOTE SENSING OF
SAVANNA'S WATER USE & STRESS

FROM LOCAL TO REGIONAL SCALE.

PROCEEDINGS

TIGER PROJECT

Proceedings

Workshop On Remote Sensing of Water Use and Water Stress in African Savanna Ecosystem from Local to Regional Scale

Ana Andreu and Timothy Dube

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Organizers: UNU-FLORES and the University of Limpopo.

Host: University of Limpopo.

Co-Conveners: Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), ITC-Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation (University of Twente), European Space Agency (ESA), South African Space Agency (SANSA), University of KwaZulu Natal.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

Savanna is among Africa's most productive landscapes, supporting livestock and rural livelihoods. Droughts and erratic rainfall patterns across large parts of Africa result in water-limited environments sensitive to climatic conditions, environmental changes, and land management practices, jeopardizing this ecosystem's productivity and resilience. **TIGER Project 410: Remote Sensing of Water Use and Water Stress in African Savanna Ecosystem from Local to Regional Scale: Implications for Land Productivity**, is a joint initiative of UNU-FLORES (Germany) and the University of Limpopo (South Africa), funded by the European Space Agency (ESA), and supported by the TIGER Capacity Building Facility (ITC- University of Twente).

The project aimed to develop a modeling framework to quantify savanna's water use and stress (Figure 1) and to determine the spatial distribution and effects of vegetation fractional cover on water resources from local to regional scales integrating EO data to support decision-making at different levels (farm, river basin). To monitor savanna ecosystem water use/stress in a semi-continuous spatiotemporal way, this project integrates two different evapotranspiration (ET) estimation approaches with different conceptual/operational capabilities and limitations. The choice of the two approaches is based on their proven ability to estimate ET over partially vegetated heterogeneous landscapes, such as savanna-type ecosystems. The high spatial and temporal resolution VIS/NIR data provided by Sentinel 2 allow a continuous monitoring of vegetation cover (from each layer) and actual evapotranspiration (Kc-FAO56). Meanwhile, thermal data provided by Sentinel 3, at lower spatial resolution, help to assess ecosystem water stress (TSEB). The procedure was tested with SPOT 5 (VIS/NIR) and AATSR (TIR). The method was validated in South African savannas (using flux towers in the Kruger National Park) and can be applied to other areas. Vegetation Fractional Cover, Reference ET, actual ET, Net Radiation, Sensible Heat Flux, Ground Heat Flux, Latent Heat Flux, and historical ET continuous values were derived over the study areas. By combining these ET-estimation approaches, savanna water use and water stress situations can be regularly monitored, providing key information to improve integrated water resources management over large areas.

Figure 1: Modeling framework of project 410

The aim of this project, to account for African savannas' water use, water stress, and the influence of different vegetation growth on water availability using Earth Observation (EO) data, has been partly covered. The project developed a modeling framework to derive a savanna water use/stress product for supporting water monitoring, validated, and applied over Kruger Park. A mechanistic understanding of how the endemic dry periods (high air temperatures and no rainfall) and the canopy structure (patched multiple canopy layers) interact with land-atmospheric processes is required to model savanna water flux at regional scales. In addition, robust techniques must be devised to determine/upscale the ecosystem parameters (differentiating between woody/non-woody vegetation) and fluxes over space and time. To assess and analyze ecosystem parameters, 2 field campaigns were conducted in Kruger, on the CSIR experimental savanna sites Skukuza & Malopeni, over the dry and the wet seasons. Ecosystem and species leaf area index measurements and radiometric information were collected from both sites to validate the estimations of the vegetation coverage properties derived from EO and characterize the areas (Figure 2). <https://vimeo.com/216811657>

Figure 2: Footprint (Schuepps et al., 1990) of Skukuza; Savanna experimental sites Malopeni and Skukuza; Precipitation and Stress Index (ESI) derived from TSEB model, for 2010.

Presentations related with the TIGER project, TIGER Initiative, ESA Sentinel missions and WOIS tool were conducted by both PIs (e.g. Pan African University Institute for Water and Energy Science in the African Union PAUWES-UNU webinars ([UNU-FLORES Webinar at PAUWES Summer School in Bonn - UNU - Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and of Resources](#)), WMO & ENVISAT training course in the use of satellite products for drought monitoring and agro-meteorological applications ([Earth Observation Tools to Build Disaster Management Capacity in Africa-UNU](#)), Nexus Seminar ([Remote Sensing for Water Management in Africa's Savannas - UNU - Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and of Resources](#)) being the results presented in several conferences and symposiums (e.g. AARSE 2016, Andreu et al., 2016; EGU 2017, Andreu et al., 2017; ISRSE 37, Dube et al., 2017; DNC 2017, Andreu et al., 2017) and the **Tiger Savanna Tool Handbook** was also published by the project team (Andreu et al., 2017), in order to be used by experts on the field. ([Remote Sensing for Monitoring Water Use and Stress in Savannas: A Handbook - UNU - Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and Resources](#)).

As one of the last actions from the TIGER project 410, the workshop on Remote Sensing of Water Use and Water Stress in the African Savanna Ecosystem was conducted at the University of

Limpopo, South Africa, with experts from all over the world, from the 20th to the 22nd of September 2017, organized by Dr. Andreu (UNU-FLORES) and Dr. Dube (University of Limpopo). ([Workshop On Remote Sensing of Water Use and Water Stress in the African Savanna Ecosystem from Local to Regional Scales - UNU - Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and Resources](#)).

1.2 Scope and Objectives

Drought periods and erratic rainfall patterns across large parts of Africa result in water-limited environments like savannas, which are highly sensitive to land management practices and climate change. Over the Southern part of the continent, savannas are key productive landscapes supporting livestock, crops, and rural livelihoods. Monitoring water use and the natural vegetation stress over these complex semi-arid ecosystems can support rangeland management to maintain long-term productivity. Quantifying water (energy) fluxes requires efficient and sound monitoring of the state variables driving their evolution, the external conditions influencing them, and the measurement of the fluxes. Remote sensing provides a unique perspective to approach these exchanges, with sensors, analytical tools, and models continuously evolving and providing new possibilities to address a complete space-time description of these land-atmosphere processes.

This workshop aimed to present and discuss the current state of art On Remote Sensing for African Savannas Water Use and Stress, with a practical (Hands-on training) approach, discussing the perspectives for the use of earth observation technology on the estimation of water and energy fluxes, with a particular focus on modeling semiarid complex natural systems evapotranspiration. This action was part of the TIGER project 410, within the TIGER Initiative framework, funded by the European Space Agency and supported by the United Nations University and the University of Limpopo.

The TIGER Savanna Tool Handbook was used (and provided): [Record #UNU:6152 Details](#)

The workshop's objectives are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Objectives of the workshop on Remote Sensing of Savanna's Water Use and Stress from Local to Regional Scale.

2. Workshop Summary

2.1 Participants

Participants (table 1 and Figure 4) come from the University of Limpopo (UL), the South African Department of Water and Sanitation (DWS), the University of KwaZulu Natal (UKZN), the University of the Free State (UFS), the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR) and the South African Space Agency (SANS), all organizations from South Africa, and the Zambian Water Resources Management Authority (ZWRMA).

Figure 4: Workshop participants Day 2 after the lunch break.

Lecturers **Nobuhle Majozi (CSIR)**, **Dr. Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)**, **Oupa Malahlela (SANS)**, and **Dr. Mbulisi Sibanda (UKZN)** were invited and funded by the organization, as well as guests from other institutions Cleta Shoko (collaborator of the TIGER project 410 from UKZN) and Samuel Adelabu (UFS). Rector Mutemba (ZWRMA) and Trylee Nyasha (UKZN) were granted complete funding for their workshop participation. **Dr. Vekerdy** and **Dr. Guzinski** participated as lecturers in online seminars.

Figure 5: Guest and trainers of the workshop. From left to right, Trylee Nyasha, Clodean Mothapo, Ana Andreu, Abel Ramoelo, Timothy Dube, and Inos Dhau.

Table 1: List of participants and attendance per day

	Organization	Name	email	Attendance		
				Day1	Day 2	Day 3
1	UNU-FLORES	-	-	x	x	x
2	UL	-	-	x	x	x
3	CSIR	-	-	x	x	x
4	CSIR	-	-	x	x	x
5	SANSA	-	-	x	x	x
6	UKZN	-	-	x	x	x
7	UKZN	-	-		x	x
8	UKZN	-	-	x	x	x
9	WRM Zambia	-	-	x	x	x
10	UFS	-	-		x	x
11	DWS SA	-	-	x	x	x
12	DWS SA	-	-	x	x	
13	DWS SA	-	-	x	x	x
14	UL	-	-	x		x
15	UL	-	-	x	x	x
16	UL	-	-	x	x	x
17	UL	-	-	x		
18	UL	-	-		x	
19	UL	-	-	x	x	x
20	UL	-	-	x	x	
21	UL	-	-	x	x	
22	UL	-	-	x	x	
23	UL	-	-	x	x	
24	UL	-	-	x		
25	UL	-	-	x	x	x
26	UL	-	-	x	x	
27	UL	-	-	x		
28	UL	-	-	x		
29	UL	-	-	x	x	
30	UL	-	-	x	x	x

31	UL	-	-	x	x	x
32	UL	-	-	x	x	
33	UL	-	-	x	x	
34	UL	-	-	x	x	
35	UL	-	-	x	x	
TOTAL of participants/day				33	30	19

2.1.1 Team of Experts

<p>Dr. Ana Andreu</p> <p>Contact: anandreu@posteo.net</p> <p>At UNU, she contributed to the Nexus Water-Soil-Waste, and she was the EU leader of the TIGER project “Remote Sensing of water use-stress in African savanna ecosystem” with Dr. Dube. She was a postdoc in the Dept. of Env. Science, Policy, and Management at the Univ. of California-Berkeley-US, with Prof. Baldocchi on dynamics over semi-arid env. Ph.D. in 2014, supervised by Dr. González-Dugo, focussed on surface energy balance components over complex Mediterranean ecosystems. She integrated remote-sensed TIR/VIS/NIR information into 2-source models and distributed soil water balance approaches on productive oak savannas, forest, and agricultural landscapes. She uses multi-scale variable-source data analysis, Earth Observation techniques, and micrometeorological techniques (Eddy Covariance, including programming, set-up of instrumentation, protocols, maintenance, and data post-processing). She participated in airborne campaigns and has expertise in radiometry and biophysical measurements for vegetation.</p>
<p>Dr. Timothy Dube</p> <p>Contact: timothydube3@gmail.com</p> <p>He holds a Bachelor’s Honours degree in Geography (2008) with two University Book prizes, a Master of Science degree in Geoinformation Science and Earth Observation for Water Resources and Environmental Management (WREM) (2012), and a Ph.D. in Environmental Science (2016). His Ph.D. was supported by the South African Applied Center for Climate and Earth Systems Science (ACCESS). The South African ACCESS supports high-quality, innovative scientific research with significant contributions to South Africa and the African continent. He has been involved intensive training across different institutions of higher learning and research organizations in South Africa (University of Witwatersrand, University of Johannesburg, South African National Space Agency (SANS), the African Association of Remote Sensing of the Environment (AARSE) and WaterNET – a Capacity Building organization for Water Resources and Environmental Management in southern Africa and abroad. In the process, he gained exceptional skills in solving complex environmental challenges across southern Africa. Timothy Dube is a senior lecturer in GIScience and Earth Observation lecturer at the University of Limpopo. He has published several articles on urban land use and land cover changes, as well as water quality using EO data in top ISI peer-reviewed journals and reviewing over 10 journal articles in the same field. He is currently</p>

involved in the TIGER Bridge African Water for Agriculture Project supported by the European Space Agency as the lead African research.
Dr. Abel Ramoelo
<p>Contact: aramoelo@csir.co.za</p> <p>Dr. Ramoelo has a Ph.D. in geoinformation science and earth observation from the University of Twente, Netherlands. His key competencies are in developing and testing remote sensing-based models to extract vegetation variables, specifically essential variables of climate and biodiversity, and using optical multispectral and hyperspectral remote sensing techniques and lidar and radar data. Ramoelo's area of interest lies in vegetation quality and quantity estimation using hyperspectral and multispectral remote sensing technologies, improving and developing techniques to extract vegetation parameters (indicators of quality and quantity) using remote sensing technologies, e.g., grass biomass and nutrients leaf nitrogen assessment, tree species identification, estimation and validation of leaf area index, fractional photosynthetic active radiation, and evapotranspiration.</p> <p>Expertise: Geoinformation science; Earth observation</p>
Nobuhle Majozi
<p>Contact: nmajozi@csir.co.za</p> <p>She holds an Honour's Bachelor's degree BSc in Water Resources Management and a Master of Science degree in Geo-information Science and Earth Observation for Water Resources and Environmental Management (WREM) (2011), where she specialized in remote sensing of water quality. She is working on her Ph.D. in Remote sensing techniques in evapotranspiration estimation in semi-arid environments under a sandwich program with the University of Twente and the Council for Scientific and Industrial Research. She has published journals in related fields, i.e., remote sensing of water quality and evapotranspiration in top ISI peer-reviewed journals, and has reviewed manuscripts in the same fields.</p>
Oupa Malahlela
Contact: omalahlela@sansa.org.za
Dr. Mbulisi Sibanda
<p>Contact: sibandambulisi@gmail.com</p> <p>Mbulisi Sibanda is a Post-doctoral research fellow at the School of Agriculture, Earth and Environmental Sciences, University of KwaZulu Natal in South Africa. He is an upcoming researcher in the field of Environmental Science, with a specific emphasis on Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation applications in vegetation mapping. He is also interested in applying geospatial technologies in mapping soil erosion, water resources, and wildlife spatial distributions. Currently, he is assessing the utility of multi- and hyperspectral remotely sensed data in rangeland ecology, agronomy, and vegetation (alien invasive species) mapping.</p>
Dr. Radoslaw Guzinski
Contact: radoslaw.guzinski@esa.int
Dr. Zoltan Vekerdy
Contact: z.vekerdy@utwente.nl

Zoltán Vekerdy is a hydrologist and remote sensing specialist who holds the position of Assistant Professor at the ITC Faculty of the University of Twente, Netherlands. He also works as Scientific Advisor at Szent István University, Hungary. He started his research carrier in the 1980s at the Water Resources Research Centre (VITUKI) in Hungary, then moved to the ITC at the beginning of the nineties. The application of Earth Observation for water management has been his primary scientific interest, focusing on environmental and agricultural aspects. Among others, he worked on several problems related to wetlands worldwide, including, among others, in Iran, China, Mexico, and several African countries. Dr. Vekerdy has supervised several young researchers at Ph.D. and MSc levels at universities in the Netherlands, Hungary, the US, South Africa, and Zambia. He (co-)authored over a hundred scientific publications, including peer-reviewed articles, book chapters, and scientific reports. Since 2008, as the Principal Investigator of the TIGER Capacity Building Facility funded by the European Space Agency, he has been coordinating the network of several hundreds of researchers working on more than sixty Earth observation research projects in the water sector of Africa.

2.2. Activities

TV White Space seminar room, from the 20th to 22nd September 2017. The workshop was planned and organized by Ana Andreu (UNU-FLORES) and Timothy Dube (UL), with lecturers from the University of KwaZulu Natal (UKZN), CSIR, SANSA, ESA, and ITC- Faculty of geo-information Science and Earth Observation. Table 2 provides detailed information on each section's final Agenda and the lecturers-facilitators. The workshop's agenda was:

1. Lectures focused on available and accessible data sources and tools.
2. Introduction of different software (SNAP, sen2cor & Anaconda)
3. Review of other interesting software (QGIS, WOIS)
4. Discuss the progress of remote sensing applications in water management in Africa (savannas).

The workshop agenda (table 2) and introduction to the installation of the software (for the participants to be familiarized with the software in advance) were distributed before the start. Due to the complexity of the software used and the broad background of the participants, the content of the Hands On was modified during the workshop, and we focused on reviewing SNAP and sen2cor software while giving a little introduction to Jupyter Notebook/Anaconda.

The workshop was opened (and closed) by the encouraging speeches of Dr. Ramudzuli, Head of the Geography Department, University of Limpopo representation (Figure 6). The training course was just possible due to the support of the University of Limpopo and the involvement of Ms. Clothean Mothapo and Director Professor P. Mafeo, keys to the workshop's success.

Figure 6: Mr. Ramudzuli's opening remarks.

During the first morning, participants attended to the lecturers to gain knowledge on the different data and tools and to have a common background before attempting the hand on training. Day 1 finished with the installation and review of the software used in the following days: SNAP and sen2cor from ESA and Anaconda (to use Python and the plugin pyTSEB from Dr. Hector Nieto). QGIS (an introductory course) and WOIS software (and the TIGER training kit) were also provided for the interested participants and shortly presented on Day 2 & Day 3.

Day 2 started with the presentation of Dr. Zoltan Vekerdy regarding the TIGER Initiative, other TIGER projects, and EO tools (WOIS and HydroTEP), and was follow-up with the training given by Dr. Andreu, where participants could try/check in their own hands some available open & accessible earth observation data and tools.

Day 3 started with some more Hands-On, with a wrap-up discussion (Figure 7) on Which Tools We Have, Which Tools We Need, and Where the Bottle Necks Are when using Earth Observation on semiarid ecosystems (Figure 4) and across Africa. The conclusions are collected in the next section.

Figure 7: 3rd-day discussion, presentation by participants.

Table 2: Final agenda

Time	Session	Speaker/facilitator
20 th		
8:00	Reception of participants	
8:35	Open speech.	Mr. Ramudzuli (UL)
9:05	Scope and goals of the workshop. African Savanna Landscape (water scarcity ecosystems). TIGER savanna project 410	Dr. Andreu (UNU-FLORES)
9:30	Water Management in Semiarid Ecosystems	Mbulisi Sibanda (UL)
10	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:30	CSIR activities Evapotranspiration: Measurement and estimation	Dr. Abel Ramoelo (CSIR) Ms. Nobuhle Majozi (CSIR)
11:45	Remote Sensing and Water Management Applications	Mr. Oupa Malahlela (SANSA)
13	Lunch break	13:00 – 14:00
14	Review of different data sources and how to download them (EO data, meteorological data, reanalysis data, etc.) – Data needed (pag. 45 of the Savanna Handbook & Annex 5) Installation of software (SNAP & sen2cor)	Dr. Andreu
15:30	European Space Agency Programs & Sentinels Missions Video Conference	Dr. Radoslaw Guzinski (ESA)
16	Coffee/Tea Break	
19	Welcoming dinner for all participants	
21 st Hands-on day		
8:30	TIGER Initiative and other TIGER projects	Dr. Zoltan Vekerdy (ITC)
10	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:30	SNAP: Detailed Steps: 1. Non-stress vegetation ET. Model framework: Kc-FAO56	Dr. Andreu
13	Lunch break	
14	SNAP: Detailed Steps: 1. Non-stress vegetation ET. Model framework: Kc-FAO56 + iCOR S2 atmospheric correction	Dr. Andreu
16	Coffee/Tea Break	
22 nd		
8:30	QGIS introductory course/WOIS training kit presentation PyTSEB. 2. Stress vegetation ET	Dr. Andreu
10	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:30	Discussion	Dr. Dube & Dr. Andreu
13	Lunch break	

2.2.1. Discussion

Participants were divided into 3 groups of 4-5 persons. Each group had to focus on one of the 3 questions (Figure 8), although this was not strictly due to the interconnections between them.

- Which tools do we have (e.g., models, EO, meteo)? Is there enough information for decision-making, or is there a need to gather additional information?
- Which tools do we need?
- Where are the bottlenecks (e.g., internet connexion, lacking methods)?

After 30 min of discussion, the representative of each group presented their findings, and finally, the rest of the workshop participants intervened with their perspectives and inputs. So each point is now a collective effort of all participants in the discussion.

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DAY 3 : DISCUSSION

-Which **TOOLS we have** (e.g. models, EO, meteo)? Is there enough information for decision-making or is there a need to gather additional information?

-Which **TOOLS we need**?

-Where are the **bottle necks** (e.g. internet connexion, lacking methods)?

Figure 8: Discussion questions of the 3rd Day.

1st GROUP, Which Tools Do We Have? (Nobuhle Majozi, Abel Ramoelo, Timothy Dube & Patrick Kaphola).

GIS and Remote Sensing tools & data

- WOIS
- SNAP
- QGIS
- ArcGis + GeoNetCost, Meteosat Second Generation - MSSG; LSASAF
- ENVI
- Receiving Stations
- Re-analysis data for climatic analysis
- SWAT models
- ILWIS
- Surface temperatures, soil moisture, evapotranspiration datasets
- FerusNet – Provide data for agriculture

Methodological tools (Data and Software)

- ECMWF – Global meteorological data providers
- World CLIM (meteo and projections of climate)
- Local weather data, Universities, Parks, Private Companies, and farmers.
- Re-analysis data for climatic analysis (ERA data, ARC, African meteo data)

- ARC, SAWS, AEON, WRC

Data providers

- NASA: Landsat, Aster, Modis
- USGS – EO and climatic
- AIRBUS – SPOT
- SANSI – Landsat datasets
- ESA - Copernicus

Nevertheless, even after integrating the data and tools collected, the main challenge remains, **do we have enough information to make conclusions, to influence policies?** To look into the stakeholder's interest and set up policies that African countries can follow?

2nd GROUP, Which Tools We Need? (Aphelele Mgabisa, Trylee Nyasha, Mabatho Mothapo, Frederick Mashao, and Clodean Mothapo).

We need ...

- users friendly specialized Remote Sensing applications (software) – e.g., for farmers. E.g., farmers want to know where/how much fertilizers they need to add to their farms.
- Data from reliable sources.
- Data at high spatial resolution: 2 – 5 m images. These datasets are expensive.
- Cheap and affordable earth observation data.
- Good Internet connection.
- More in situ data collection and more datasets to validate.
- To quantify water volume! We need to determine the water quantity and where the reservoirs are to know how much water we must manage. We also need to account for the sedimentation rates, which are challenging to determine.
- Robust classification methods.

3rd GROUP, What are the bottlenecks (BN) and the challenges? (Cleta Shoko, Mbulisi Sibanda, Ana Andreu & Simon Moloele).

1. Coordination between all organizations. The lack of coordination and the people working in isolation is a significant bottleneck. It needs to be clarified which organization/person is doing what, and different institutions from the same country ask for the same funding. Some researchers do not add knowledge to the previous one because it is not coordinated, and the work is redundant. Possible solutions are: to meet, to have common goals, to have communities for EO for water, not to force collaboration but to coordinate, to have a community of Practices, and to define Societal Benefits Areas: key themes where the countries should focus.
2. Information/knowledge transfer intra/inter organizations. The transfer of skills and knowledge is also a challenge. People tend to keep/hold the information. Even internally. It is also difficult to transfer knowledge between different generations. More conservative people usually do not want to use new technologies. Also, integrating these technologies can eliminate working spots and jobs.
3. Internet connection (which sometimes provokes the necessity to rely on other institutions)
4. Expertise. Even with good, freely available data sets, we need the technical expertise to analyze and process the data to transfer helpful information to the stakeholders.

5. Collaboration between agencies and stakeholders is challenging. We need official agreements and contracts to set up procedures to follow.
6. Integrating different scales is a challenge, and how we upscale local experiments to be implemented on a regional or global scale (policies).
7. Involve stakeholders and how we translate the scientific results into information we all understand. How do we cross the gap between practitioners and academics? Is publishing papers essential, or having the information ready for the stakeholders?
8. The issue of data storage capacity.
9. Remote Sensing in Africa needs to be better appreciated. It has yet to be fully embraced. That can affect funding. People may fear losing their jobs because they will not be relevant anymore.
10. Lack of in situ data, soil moisture, and soil data for models. There are few weather stations, and the number is reducing.
11. Lack of high-resolution data (cm to m). UAVs are expensive.
12. Accessibility. Some areas are not accessible due to licenses, cost, etc.
13. Funding is a great challenge.
14. To share, integrate and make accessible the information. Moreover, to expose the people to this information for them to be involved.

2.3 Evaluation

Nineteen participants filled out the survey.

1. Not relevant.
2. Not relevant.
3. Savanna Tool: What are the social and economic uses of savannas in your country, if some?
 - o Agriculture – 30%
 - o Tourism – 25%
 - o Grazing – 25%
 - o Traditional medicine – 20%
 - o Other/explain:
 - o Biodiversity.
 - o Livelihoods, settlements, hunting, and trading of gravel and sand.
 - o Nature conservation area for small to large herbivores.
 - o Livestock, e.g., cattle farming.
4. Savanna Tool: What are the major threats facing savannas in your country?
 - o Fire – 20%
 - o Climate variability – 19%
 - o Overgrazing – 24%
 - o Exotic species – 16%
 - o Clearance of land for agriculture and human settlement – 21%
 - o Other:
 - o Threaten ecosystem equilibrium.
 - o Clearance for collection of wood, hunting, and housing.
 - o Use of the lands as open dumps for waste.
5. Savanna Tool: Have you and your department/ministry used any tools utilizing Earth Observation (EO) data? **79% YES** - 21% NO

If yes, please explain some of the tools used.

- Satellite images (mostly Landsat, SPOT 5, aerial photographs, Sentinel 2) from platforms such as Earth Explorer.
- GIS and remote sensing.
- Software such as QGIS, SNAP, ERDAS, ESRI, etc.
- To assess: wildlife distribution, changes in ecosystems, fire occurrence and spatial distribution, the impact of alien invasive species on natural vegetation, land use, land cover mapping, estimation of biomass and carbon stocks, etc.

6. Savanna Tool: What is the EO data public availability level in your country?

- EO data in South Africa are freely available (Landsat, MODIS), but some constraints limit accessibility. That caused that finally, data is only accessible to well-developed institutions. High spatial resolution (cm) data are not affordable.
- If you are a student or other institution, data is also available from data distributors such as SANSA.
- There is still room for improvement, although it partially improved.
- EO is a new technology (also a lack of expertise) that can hinder the use of EO data.
- 9 participants: Basic (2)/Medium (1)/Moderately high (4)/Good to very good (2)

7. Savanna Tool: What technological challenges do you face in accessing and interpreting EO data?

- Lack of reliable internet access to download data – 35%
- Lack of enough storage capacity for data downloaded – 33%
- Lack of human resource capacity to process and interpret the data – 32%
- Other (please explain):
 - Financial constraints, poor computers.
 - Lack of personnel and lack of workshops to provide skills to learn how to use the interfaces and how to interpret data.
 - Lack of appreciation by the government and institutions at large, and GIS and RS need to be better marketed in this country.

8. Savanna Tool: What is the technical know-how level in interpreting the data from EO and using it in monitoring tools in your department?

- None (1): No one in our department has been exposed to or is aware of the tool.
- Basic (4): Training is required in interpreting the data from EO and using it in monitoring tools.
- Medium (3): A limited number of individuals have the ability.
- Moderate (4): There is a team of EO scientists, junior to level level.
- Good (5)

9. Savanna Tool: Would there be a need for extensive training on the use of the tool and how to interpret the results? **94% YES – 6% NO**

If yes, please highlight the areas you wish covered during training sessions.

- Advanced statistical modeling of EO data.
- Water Bodies, Flood Mapping and Monitoring, land use mapping.

- Pre-processing of remotely sensed data.
- Understanding various ecosystem elements to draw informed decisions for planning, monitoring, and managing environmental resources.
- Water use in agriculture, land degradation assessment, and water quality assessment in a savanna environment.
- Real-life scenarios and case studies.
- Training in programming (use of R and Python).
- Modeling environmental problems using EO.
- The socioeconomically integrated part of GIS and RS in addressing real challenges like poverty, unemployment, and social well-being.
- Everything...QGIS, Python, etc.

10. Savanna Tool: What would be needed to sustain the use of the tool in the long term and have it implemented in your country?

- Enough training (and funding) to equip people with skills to be productive and generate revenue for self-sustenance.
- More training kits on the pre-processing and analysis of EO data.
- Informed me of the update!
- A lengthened training session for the South African experts using this tool will be beneficial.
- To further the awareness about human impacts on Savanna and challenges, to get more attention from the stakeholders.
- Capacity building activities on universities and institutions.
- Introducing the tools and applications at early stages.
- Making them freely available and user-friendly.

11. Savanna Tool: Who would be considered the major stakeholders to use the tool, and what would their role be in its implementation?

- Research and Education Institutions, such as Universities – Academics
 - Students and lecturers (they will encourage other students – Down-Top techniques)
 - Geo-Information Society of South Africa
- Tiger Initiative Capacity – to offer capacity Building
- Governmental departments (Department of Agriculture and Environment, Dept. of Water and Sanitation, Dept. of Human Settlements, Dept. of Rural Development and Land Reform) – Authorities, policymakers
 - National Parks and Wildlife
 - SANSA
- Private sector
 - Farmers
 - Rangeland managers
- Communities

12. Overall impression: What is your overall assessment of the workshop? Please give a mark (0 worst – 100 best).

- a. 80 – 90: 56%

b. 70 – 80: 39%

c. 60 – 70: 6%

- (c): Although not very high, it is by no means an indication of the presenters and organizers. I would have loved the opportunity to spend more time getting to familiarize myself with the various programs. For the amount of information to assimilate and given that I am an absolute novice in this field, I would have preferred that the workshop be at least one week. Two weeks would have been ideal.

13. Overall impression: I recommend this workshop to my colleagues.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		16%	84%	

14. Organization, logistics: The support I got from the Organizers before coming to the University of Limpopo was sufficient.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
6%		22%	72%	

15. Organization, logistics: The information provided by UNU-FLORES / UL before coming to the workshop was good.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
6%		11%	83%	

16. Organization, and logistics: The tea/coffee breaks were good.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		11%	89%	

The catering was perfect.

17. Organization and logistics: The facilities at UL were suitable for carrying out the workshop.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		17%	78%	6%

A larger hall can do better next time.

More space to accommodate enough people.

18. Lectures and practical exercises: The workshop program was well-designed.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		28%	72%	

More time should be allocated to training.

The wifi in this university was a challenge.

The course was extremely rushed for the amount of information to digest and grasp. The organizers would have done well to extend the workshop whereby candidates who were novices could have had more time to ask questions and get more hands-on experience.

19. Workshop content: I had sufficient background knowledge for the workshop.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
20%	10%	20%	50%	

It was too scientific.

There were many technicalities of which it was my first time. Still, one can improve from here.

Being a novice with no experience in remote sensing, I had little to no prior knowledge or exposure to the content and programs provided

* There were different groups of participants regarding the background: from no background to medium to experts. The workshop target group should be defined in advance, and attendance should be limited to the specific target group (basic/medium/expert workshop)

20. Course content: The subject of the workshop was Savanna Water Use and Water Stress Tool. What is your opinion about the level of the lectures?

It was too basic for me; I already knew most of the presented materials.	
It was just fine; I learned a lot.	67%
It was too advanced; I did not understand most of the lectures.	28%
Other (please specify):	6%

I have learned a lot, but some of the lectures I did not understand.

It was most informative as I learned a lot. However, I would have appreciated more time.

21. The access to supervision/scientific help during the workshop was good.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		16%	84%	

22. Indicate in this matrix if the objective was met.

Objective was...	Met	Partly met	Not met
Review Savanna Water Use and Water Stress Tool.	78%	17%	6%
Build skills on estimating ET using different methods and software	33.3%	55.6%	11.1%
Discuss/review methods and algorithms and their implementation.	71%	18%	12%

23. Indicate in this matrix the quality of the following program sections.

All in %	Very good	Good	Moderate	Bad	Very bad
Welcome and introduction. Scope and goals of the workshop.	78	22			
African Savanna Landscape (water scarcity ecosystems).	28	61	11		
Water Management in Semiarid Ecosystems.	41	47	12		
Evapotranspiration: measurements and estimation.	59	29	12		
Remote Sensing and Water Management Applications.	65	29	6		
European Space Agency Programs. Sentinels.	50	44	6		
TIGER Initiative and other TIGER projects.	61	28	11		
Installation of the different tools and preparation of PC.	22	39	39		
Presentation of different data sources.	22	67	11		
Hands-On.	28	22	44	6	
Discussion.	50	33	17		

* Hands-on 50% good, 50% not good. This section should be slowly planned for the next workshop.

24. Workshop content: In my future activities, I will certainly use the knowledge I gained during this workshop.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		21%	79%	

25. Workshop content: I will use the software/data presented in future activities.

Disagree	More disagree than agree	More agree than disagree	Agree	Not relevant
		17%	83%	

26. Recommendations: What follow-up to this workshop do you recommend?

- More training.
- Online guidance on the tools if needed.
- Prepare manuals with detailed step-by-step procedures for image processing and analysis.
- Assess whether the students at the host University have understood various data products available and their applications.
- Sharing any advances, successes, or limitations in the application of the tool.
- Updates on recent and helpful software and available data.
- I am incredibly grateful that the organizers and presenter provided me with their details to allow me to contact them should I need assistance.

27. Recommendations: Any other remark you want to make can be made below!

- More time should be allocated for training. The time was insufficient to grasp the use of all software.
- Next time, the workshop should be longer so that we can get complete basic skills on using all the tools more precisely and straightforwardly.
- I felt that I would have loved the opportunity to spend more time getting to familiarize myself with the various programs. For the amount of information that one has to digest and assimilate during the workshop and given that I am an absolute novice in this field, I would have preferred that the workshop be a minimum of one week. Two weeks would have been ideal.
- We want more demonstrations of using software such as Anaconda, Snap, and Sen2Cor, as well as an extension of the workshop days for at least 5 days.
- I recommend that they extend the workshop days maybe to a week.
- Reduce the number of days to 2.
- Increase the number of days during the workshop and reduce discussions and instead focus on practicals.
- I recommend that more practice be done to understand how to use the tools.
- More precise and straightforward approach.
- More hands-on practicals.
- Know more about the software and scripts for atmospheric correction.
- Help people to install the software without moving fast.
- I am grateful to the organizers. We need more of these capacity-building workshops.
- I am so grateful to the workshop organizers. We benefited abundantly despite minor hiccups such as the Internet services. We need more of these capacity-building workshops.

- I would like to thank the organizers and sponsors for such an informative seminar/educational session.
- Thanks to the organizers and sponsors of the workshop for giving us an educational session on the application of remote sensing.
- Thank you for allowing me to attend...
- Let's have this kind of workshop at least once a year.
- This workshop should be held more often to improve our knowledge, skills for using technology tools as well as improving our skills for data interpretation.
- Continue to hold this kind of workshop in South Africa.

Annexes

Annex 1: Agenda

WORKSHOP ON REMOTE SENSING OF SAVANNA'S WATER USE & STRESS FROM LOCAL TO REGIONAL SCALE.

University of Limpopo, Wednesday 20th to Friday 22nd September, 2017

Drought periods and erratic rainfall patterns across large parts of Africa result in water-limited environments like savannas, highly sensitive to land management practices and changes in climate. Over the Southern part of the continent, savannas are key productive landscapes supporting livestock, crops and rural livelihoods. Monitoring water use and the natural vegetation stress over these semi-arid complex ecosystems can support rangeland management, to maintain long-term productivity. Quantifying water (energy) fluxes requires an efficient and sound monitoring of the state variables driving their evolution, the external conditions influencing them, and the measurement of the fluxes. Remote sensing provides a unique perspective to approach these exchanges, with sensors, analytical tools and models continuously evolving and providing new possibilities to address a more complete space-time description of these land-atmosphere processes.

This workshop aims to present the current state of art On Remote Sensing for African Savannas Water Use and Stress, with a practical (Hands on training) approach, discussing the perspectives for the use of earth observation technology on the estimation of water and energy fluxes, with a special focus on modelling semiarid complex natural systems evapotranspiration. This action is part of the TIGER project 410, within the TIGER Initiative framework, funded by the European Space Agency, and support by the United Nations University, the University of Limpopo and the University of Western Cape.

For the workshop, the TIGER Savanna Tool Handbook will be used (and provided):

<http://collections.unu.edu/view/UNU:6152>

<https://flores.unu.edu/en/news/news/remote-sensing-for-monitoring-water-use-and-stress-in-savannas-a-handbook.html>

WORKSHOP ON REMOTE SENSING OF SAVANNA'S WATER USE & STRESS FROM LOCAL TO REGIONAL SCALE

Schedule

Time	Session	Presenter
20 th		
8:00 – 8:30	Reception of participants	
8:35 – 9:00	Open remarks and introduction. Scope and goals of the workshop.	Prof. Mafeo (UL) & Dr. Ramudzuli (UL)
9:05 – 10:00	African Savanna Landscape (water scarcity ecosystems). TIGER savanna project 410	Dr. Andreu (UNU-FLORES) & Dr. Dube (UL)
10:00 – 10:30	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:35 – 11:30	Water Management in Semiarid Ecosystems	To confirm: UL or UKZN
11:35 – 13:00	Evapotranspiration: measurement and estimation	Ms. Nobuhle Majozi & Dr. Abel Ramoelo (CSIR)
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break	
14:00 – 15:30	Remote Sensing and Water Management Applications	Mr. Oupa Malahlela (SANSA)
15:30 – 16:00	Coffee/Tea Break	
16:00 – 17:30	European Space Agency Programs – Sentinels	Dr. Radoslaw Guzinski (ESA)
19:00	Welcoming dinner (for all participants)	
21 st Hands on day		
8:30 – 10:00	TIGER Initiative and other TIGER projects	Dr. Zoltan Vekerdy (ITC)
10:00 – 10:30	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:35 – 11:00	Review of installation of the different tools (software)	Dr. Andreu & Dr. Dube
11:05 – 11:30	Presentation of different data sources	
11:35 – 13:00	Hands On (Steps for the Savanna Tool)	
13:05 – 14:00	Lunch break	
14:00 – 15:30	Hands On (Steps for the Savanna Tool)	
15:30 – 16:00	Coffee/Tea Break	
16:05 – 17:30	Hands On (Steps for the Savanna Tool)	
22 nd		
8:30 – 10:00	Hands On	
10:00 – 10:30	Coffee/Tea Break	
10:35 – 13:00	Discussion (Savanna problems - Application of the Tool) Feedback	
13:00 – 14:00	Lunch break	

UL: University of Limpopo.
 UNU-FLORES: United Nations University, Institute for Integrated Management of Materials Fluxes and of Resources, Germany.
 UKZN: University of KwaZulu Natal.
 CSIR: Council for Scientific and Industrial Research. SANSA: South African Space Agency.
 ESA: European Space Agency, Rome.
 ITC: ITC-Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation, University of Twente.

Annex 2: Certificate

WORKSHOP ON REMOTE SENSING OF
SAVANNA'S WATER USE & STRESS
FROM LOCAL TO REGIONAL SCALE.

TIGER PROJECT

CERTIFICATE OF ATTENDANCE

This is to certify that

has attended the workshop
On Remote Sensing of Water Use and Stress
in African Savanna

held on the University of Limpopo
from September 20 to 22, 2017

Dr. Andreu (UNU-FLORES) Dr. Dube (University of Limpopo)

Annex 3: Flyer

WORKSHOP ON REMOTE SENSING OF SAVANNA'S WATER USE & STRESS FROM LOCAL TO REGIONAL SCALE.

TIGER PROJECT

20 - 22 SEPTEMBER 2017
UNIVERSITY OF LIMPOPO

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For registration, send the form to: anandream@posteo.net
Before 10 of September 2017.

DAY 1 (8h to 19h): THEORY

African Savanna Landscape - water scarcity ecosystems
Water Management in Semi-arid Ecosystems
Evapotranspiration: measurement and estimation
Remote Sensing and Water Management Applications
European Space Agency Programs - Sentinels
TIGER initiative

DAY 2 (9h to 19h): HANDS ON

Different softwares (QGIS, PYTHON, SNAP)
Different data sources (where/how to download them)
Savanna Water Use and Stress Tool - How To

DAY 3 (9h to 14h): DISCUSSION

Discussion
Feedback

**UNITED NATIONS
UNIVERSITY**

UNU-FLORES

**Institute for Integrated Management
of Material Fluxes and of Resources**

The United Nations University Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and of Resources (UNU-FLORES) was established in Dresden, Germany in 2012 with the support of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) and the Ministry for Higher Education, Research and the Arts (SMWK) of the Free State of Saxony, Germany. As part of the United Nations University (UNU), the Institute helps build a bridge between the academic world and the United Nations. UNU encompasses 13 research and training institutes and programmes located in 12 countries around the world. UNU as a whole aims to develop sustainable solutions for pressing global problems of human survival and development.

UNU-FLORES develops strategies to resolve pressing challenges in the area of sustainable use and integrated management of environmental resources such as soil, water and waste. Focusing on the needs of the UN and its member states, particularly developing countries and emerging economies, the Institute engages in research, capacity development, advanced teaching and training as well as dissemination of knowledge. In all activities, UNU-FLORES advances a nexus approach to the sustainable management of environmental resources.

Find more information under: flores.unu.edu

ADVANCING A NEXUS APPROACH TO THE SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT OF ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES

United Nations University

Institute for Integrated Management of Material Fluxes and of Resources (UNU-FLORES)
Ammonstrasse 74 01067 Dresden, Germany
Tel.: +49 351 8921 9370 | Fax.: +49 351 8921 9389
Email: flores@unu.edu

flores.unu.edu